

Improved accounting of the health costs of air pollution in the United States

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Abstract

Air pollution exposure poses health and economic burdens, but most assessments of air pollution in the United States do not account for known variation in costs of hospital admissions and emergency department (ED) visits by race/ethnicity or region, nor do they include ambulatory care and other health-related costs. Given that medical cost data are used regularly in policy and regulatory analyses of air pollution, it is important that these data be finely resolved and comprehensive. We estimate hospital admission and ED visit costs by region, race/ethnicity, and payer type for cardiovascular, respiratory, and neurological health outcomes associated with fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) exposure that are included in the Environmental Benefits Mapping and Analysis Program–Community Edition. We also determine additional costs associated with outpatient surgeries, home health care, and prescribed medicines. We then apply these cost data to PM_{2.5} air quality improvement scenarios to assess their effect on monetized benefit totals. Regional hospital admission and ED visit costs differ from the national average by as much as –34% to +65%. Asian Americans incur the highest per-event costs for most outcomes. White and Black Americans generally incur below-average per-event costs for hospital admissions, and Black and Hispanic Americans incur below-average per-event costs for ED visits. Additional costs greatly increase the total cost of medical events for cardiovascular disease outcomes and hospital admissions for Parkinson’s disease and respiratory diseases (ages ≤18). When stratifying medical costs by race/ethnicity and region and including additional costs, monetized benefits increase by 64% under the revised National Ambient Air Quality Standard for annual PM_{2.5} exposure. The effect of cost stratification is less pronounced in scenarios in which PM_{2.5} reductions are more widespread. We recommend that stratified health cost data be used in policy and regulatory analysis, particularly in work considering health equity implications of air pollution exposure.

1. Introduction

Ambient air pollution exposure is the leading environmental risk factor for disease globally [1], and long-term exposure to fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) causes 100,000–200,000 premature deaths in the United States each year [2–4]. In addition to premature mortality, long-term PM_{2.5} exposure is associated with cardiovascular, respiratory, and nervous system effects [5,6], which can lead to hospital admissions and emergency department (ED) visits that result in economic burdens from medical costs and lost wages [7]. Average PM_{2.5} concentrations in the United States decreased nearly 40% from 2000 to 2023 [8]. These air quality improvements, largely spurred by U.S. Clean Air Act (CAA) regulations, have produced substantial health and economic benefits.

The 1990 CAA Amendments, for example, are estimated to have provided \$12 trillion (2006 U.S. dollars) in benefits from 1990–2020, outweighing compliance costs of \$380 billion by a factor of more than 30:1 [9]. In 2020 alone, the 1990 CAA Amendments provided \$3.1 billion (2006 U.S. dollars) in benefits from avoided hospital admissions and ED visits related to PM_{2.5} and O₃ exposure [9]. Such analyses require accurate and reliable estimates of the costs of hospital admissions and ED visits, which help to inform our understanding of the economic value of air quality changes in the United States.

The Environmental Benefits Mapping and Analysis Program–Community Edition (BenMAP–CE) [10], developed by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), is a widely used tool for estimating the health and economic effects of changes in air pollution exposure. EPA regularly uses BenMAP–CE in regulatory impact analyses of proposed CAA regulations, including the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) [11]. BenMAP–CE can estimate hospital admissions and ED visit costs associated with air quality changes. Many of these cost data are derived from the Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project (HCUP), a set of databases compiled by the U.S. Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality that track healthcare spending and use in the United States. With the exception of wage data, health cost data in BenMAP–CE represent national averages, which obscure well-documented differences in healthcare utilization and spending by race/ethnicity [12–15] and region of the country [16,17]. Black adult populations, for example, spend less on and use fewer primary and other recommended healthcare services but use more ED services than White adult populations [14,15]. Racial/ethnic differences in healthcare spending are not driven entirely by differing utilization rates; they also depend on differences in the price and intensity of services (i.e. spending per visit) across racial/ethnic groups [12]. At least in commercial insurance markets, regional differences in health care spending mainly result from price markups by health care providers and not differences in utilization rates by region [17].

Past research has shown the importance of using highly spatially resolved exposure estimates [18–21] and baseline mortality and morbidity rates [19,20,22] to accurately estimate air pollution health burdens; other studies have found marked differences in air pollution health burdens by race/ethnicity depending on whether concentration–response functions [23,24] or baseline mortality and morbidity rates [23–25] are stratified by race/ethnicity. These steps precede economic valuation in the air quality and health impact modeling chain. Little if any research has explored the use of health cost data stratified by race/ethnicity or region, despite known differences in costs across populations and geographies and the mounting health harms linked to PM_{2.5} exposure [5,6]. This research gap has been acknowledged in part by EPA; the BenMAP–CE user manual states that evidence on valuation estimates stratified by race/ethnicity is lacking [10]. Beyond health cost stratification, existing research suggests that default BenMAP–CE data underestimate the costs associated with hospital admissions for cardiovascular and respiratory diseases by 35–43% since they do not account for ambulatory care costs (e.g. outpatient care, home health care), costs of prescribed medicines, and other hospitalization costs [26].

This study builds on existing research by deriving hospital admission and ED visit cost data that are stratified by race/ethnicity, region, and expected payer type and by compiling additional health-related costs that are associated with hospital admissions and ED visits. First, we calculate average hospital admission and ED visit costs stratified by race/ethnicity, region, and expected payer for cardiovascular, respiratory, and neurological health outcomes in BenMAP–CE that are causally or

likely to be causally associated with PM_{2.5} exposure [5,6]. Next, we determine additional costs resulting from outpatient surgeries, home health care, and prescribed medicines associated with hospital admissions and ED visits. Finally, we assess the effect of using these cost data in place of default BenMAP–CE data on monetized benefits in the following PM_{2.5} air quality improvement scenarios: the revised 2024 NAAQS standard for PM_{2.5} [27], the three proposed alternative PM_{2.5} NAAQS standards, and an illustrative uniform air quality improvement scenario. This study is the first to assess the effects of using race/ethnicity–specific and regional health care cost data in PM_{2.5}-related health and economic impact assessment in the United States, which allows for a more finely resolved assessment of the economic burden of air pollution.

2. Methods

2.1. Health care, population, and income datasets

Hospital admission and ED visit utilization and cost data are derived from two HCUP databases: the National Inpatient Sample (NIS) [28] and the National Emergency Department Sample (NEDS) [29], the largest publicly available all-payer databases of hospital admissions and ED visits in the United States. We use data from 2019 to avoid confounding effects of changes in healthcare utilization patterns brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic [30]. Default BenMAP–CE values are derived from 2016 NIS and NEDS datasets. Hospital admission and ED visit data are supplemented with elective outpatient surgery data from HCUP’s National Ambulatory Surgery Sample (NASS) [31] and home health care and prescribed medicine data from the Medical Expenditure Panel Survey (MEPS) [32]. Methods described here are adapted in part from those from Limaye et al. [33].

HCUP datasets are stratified samples, so data are weighted to produce nationally and regionally representative estimates. We use the “svydesign” function from the R package “survey” to account for the complex sample design of HCUP datasets when calculating counts, means, and standard errors. Our method returns identical results to those produced by example SAS code provided by HCUP [34] that describes statistical methods for producing weighted estimates. See Section S1 in the Supplementary Materials for more details.

NIS data are available for the nine Census Divisions whereas NEDS and NASS data are available for the four Census Regions. HCUP datasets include six expected payer types: “Medicare,” “Medicaid,” “Private insurance,” “Self-pay,” “No charge” (e.g. charity care, medically indigent) and “Other” (e.g. worker’s compensation, Title V Maternal and Child and Health Services Block Grant, Indian Health Service division of the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs). HCUP classifies racial/ethnic groups into uniform groups that standardize data initially reported by HCUP Data Partners (see Section S2 in the Supplementary Materials for a list of HCUP partners). HCUP datasets include six racial/ethnic groups: “White,” “Black,” “Hispanic,” “Asian or Pacific Islander” (which we abbreviate as “Asian”), “Native American,” and “Other” (i.e. two or more races or unspecified). Ethnicity takes precedence over race in HCUP classifications; individuals of any race who are Hispanic are considered to be Hispanic alone.

We combine weighted discharge counts from HCUP datasets with 2019 population counts from the U.S. Census Bureau to calculate baseline hospital admission and ED visit rates [35]. The Census Bureau classifies racial groups as follows: “White,” “Black or African American,” “American Indian or Alaska Native,” “Asian,” “Native Hawaiian and Other Pacific Islander,” and “Two or more races.” An individual of any of these racial groups can be classified as “Hispanic” or “Not Hispanic.” We align racial/ethnic groups reported by the Census Bureau with those in HCUP datasets using mutually exclusive pairings (Table S1). In air quality improvement scenarios (see Section 2.3), we modify BenMAP–CE configuration files to use race/ethnicity–specific population data that align with racial/ethnic groups in HCUP (Table S1). BenMAP–CE does not include a population subgroup corresponding to “Other” in HCUP datasets, so this group is not included from the air quality improvement scenarios.

We use median per-capita annual income data from the U.S. Census Bureau’s 2019 American Community Survey (five-year estimates) [36]. County-level income data for the total population (i.e. not stratified by race/ethnicity) are used to calculate time costs associated with medical events (see Section 2.2). We use income data resolved at the Census Division level and stratified by race/ethnicity to compare per-capita income to per-capita medical benefits in air quality improvement scenarios.

2.2. Estimation of hospital admission and ED visit costs

We use HCUP data to derive utilization rates and costs for all hospital admission and ED visit types that are included in BenMAP–CE (version 1.5.8) and associated with PM_{2.5} exposure [10]. We map health impact functions in BenMAP–CE to their applicable valuation functions to produce a list of all combinations of functions that might appropriately be used in analysis. Our results focus on a subset of hospital admission and ED visit types that EPA has found to be suitable for use in PM_{2.5} benefits assessments [37] and were included in EPA’s 2022 regulatory impact analysis for PM_{2.5} NAAQS [11]: hospital admissions for Alzheimer’s disease (ages ≥65), cardiovascular diseases (ages ≥65), Parkinson’s disease (ages ≥65), respiratory diseases (ages ≤18), and respiratory diseases (ages ≥65); and ED visits for cardiovascular diseases (all ages) and respiratory diseases (all ages). Valuation functions for hospital admissions for cardiovascular diseases (ages ≥65) and respiratory diseases (ages ≥65) respectively correspond to “Cardio-, cerebro-, and peripheral vascular disease” and “Respiratory-2” in BenMAP–CE.

HCUP datasets report charges, which are converted to costs using hospital-specific cost-to-charge ratios [38]. Charges reflect the amount a hospital bills for services rendered in connection with a medical event; costs reflect the actual expenses incurred to deliver services. Charges and costs are both distinct from payments, which reflect the amounts hospitals ultimately receive as reimbursement for services [39,40]. EPA methodology assumes that costs are more suitable than charges for use in regulatory impact analysis since charges do not account for negotiations between health care providers and payers that can alter medical costs [10].

Hospital admission and ED visit data in BenMAP–CE represent groups of related diseases with primary diagnosis codes defined by the International Classification of Diseases, 9th revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-9-CM). ICD-9-CM codes in BenMAP–CE are matched to their corresponding ICD-10-CM codes, which are used in HCUP datasets, using a processed version of

the General Equivalence Mappings developed by the U.S. Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services and provided by the National Bureau of Economic Research [41]. Alzheimer’s disease and Parkinson’s disease hospital admissions in BenMAP–CE report medical costs associated with disease burdens over multiple years as well as for a single year; to focus our study on annual costs, we include only annual cost estimates for these disease types.

Hospital admission, ED visit, and outpatient surgery costs are derived from HCUP datasets by successively restricting datasets to medical events matching ICD-10-CM primary diagnosis codes and age ranges for each BenMAP–CE endpoint. Calculations described here are also repeated after restricting datasets to each combination of race/ethnicity, region, and expected payer type.

The cost of outpatient surgeries associated with an event (e.g. hospital admission or ED visit) is taken as the ratio of the number of electric outpatient surgeries to the number of events, multiplied by the average outpatient surgery cost. This method is used because individual patients are not identifiable in HCUP datasets; this ratio therefore reflects the average number (and cost) of outpatient surgeries per event, not per patient. NEDS data include the discharge status of ED visits; this is used to determine the fraction of ED visits that result in hospital admission. This fraction is multiplied by the average hospital admission cost to determine the per-event cost of hospital stays originating in the emergency department.

When stratifying HCUP data by region and race/ethnicity simultaneously, data for 23 of 318 outcomes are derived from ≤ 10 events, which are suppressed to comply with HCUP privacy protection requirements [42]. All such outcomes are hospital admission types, which are reported by Census Division, so calculations are repeated using data aggregated by Census Region or national data until outcomes are derived from > 10 events. Two “No charge” estimates are suppressed when stratifying events by expected payer type and cannot be imputed.

Home health care and prescribed medicine costs are derived from MEPS by linking the Medical Conditions File (HC-214), which includes ICD-10-CM primary diagnosis codes, with person identifiers, which includes a patient’s age. Home health care costs are estimated as the average cost from the Home Health Visits File (HC-213H) multiplied by the fraction of HCUP-derived hospital admissions or ED visits discharged with a recommendation of home health care. Prescribed medicine costs are calculated by linking the Prescribed Medicines File (HC-213A) with the Hospital Inpatient Stays File (HC-213D) and Emergency Room Visits File (HC-213E) by medical condition, event identifier, and person identifier to determine the average number and cost of prescribed medicines per hospital admission or ED visit. MEPS data cannot be stratified in the same ways as HCUP data, so values derived from MEPS reflect national averages.

BenMAP–CE medical cost data, reported in 2015 U.S. dollars, are inflation-adjusted to 2019 U.S. dollars using data from the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics on the Consumer Price Index data for medical care [43]. Lost wages associated with hospital stays are taken as the average length of stay (in days) multiplied by the county-level median daily wage, which we calculate by dividing the median annual wage by 52×5 , which is the method EPA uses in BenMAP–CE [10]. We make simplifying assumptions about the length of ED visits, outpatient surgery events, and home health care visits. Current BenMAP–CE methodology assumes that there is no time cost associated with an ED visit. The average length of an ED visit has been estimated to be 197 minutes [44], and past

research has estimated the average time patients spend traveling, waiting, and receiving services for an outpatient visit to be 121 minutes [45]. We assume that each ED visit lasts four hours (240 minutes); lost wages per ED visit therefore equal half the median daily wage. We assume that home health care visits last two hours (120 minutes), so lost wages associated with home health care are taken as one quarter of the number of days per year spent in home health care multiplied by the median daily wage. Similarly, we assume that the average outpatient visit lasts two hours (120 minutes). Though these values may be imprecise, we quantify them since it is recommended that indirect health-related costs, such as the time costs associated with receiving care, be included in analysis [46].

We use the following terms to refer to various cost types throughout this study. “Medical costs” refer to hospital admission and/or ED visit costs. “Additional costs” refer to the combined costs from outpatient surgeries, home health care, prescribed medicines, and costs of hospital stays originating in the emergency department. “Total costs” refer to the combined costs from hospital admissions and/or ED visits, all additional costs, and lost wages. “Default costs” refer to medical costs using standard BenMAP–CE cost inputs. “Updated costs” refer to medical costs using our newly derived HCUP cost data for hospital admissions and/or ED visits.

2.3. Air quality improvement scenarios

We first apply our cost data to the health benefits projected to occur under the 2024 revision to the PM_{2.5} NAAQS [11]. The revised standard lowered the allowable annual level from 12 µg/m³ to 9 µg/m³ and left the daily level unchanged at 35 µg/m³. We model effects for this revised standard (9/35 µg/m³) using the same air quality surfaces and BenMAP–CE configuration files used by EPA in its 2022 regulatory impact analysis for the PM_{2.5} NAAQS revision [11], which were provided to us by EPA staff. We use outputted BenMAP–CE files that report changes in hospital admission and ED visit counts and apply our cost data in Python (version 3.8.5).

EPA simulated PM_{2.5} concentrations using the Community Multiscale Air Quality (CMAQ) model (version 5.3.2) for 2016 to provide a base year reference simulation and again with simulated emissions for 2032 with other inputs (e.g. meteorology, initial and boundary conditions) unchanged at 2016 values. Emissions inventories were taken from the 2016 Emissions Modeling Platform (version 2) and projected to 2032. The modeling domain includes an outer domain (36US3), which covers much of Canada, Mexico, and the United States at a resolution of 36 km × 36 km and is used to provide boundary conditions, and a nested inner domain (12US1) at a 12 km × 12 km resolution, which covers the contiguous United States. See EPA’s regulatory impact analysis for more information on air quality scenario development [11].

The baseline scenario against which the NAAQS attainment scenario is compared assumes that existing EPA air regulations have been implemented and any additional emission reductions are assessed to attain the previous primary annual/daily PM_{2.5} NAAQS standards of 12/35 µg/m³. EPA air rules modeled in the baseline scenario include longstanding regulations and recently promulgated rules that are expected to take full effect by 2032 [47–49], the year in which the regulatory impact analysis assumes that attainment of the revised standard will be required.

We next model health effects under the three alternative PM_{2.5} NAAQS scenarios modeled by EPA, which assume primary annual/daily standard levels of 10/35 µg/m³, 10/30 µg/m³, and 8/35 µg/m³. These scenarios follow the same procedures described above for the revised 9/35 µg/m³ standards. Lastly, we model a uniform air quality improvement scenario in which PM_{2.5} concentrations in all CMAQ grid cells are reduced by 0.25 µg/m³ relative to the baseline scenario described above; this concentration change is similar to the mean concentration change in the 9/35 µg/m³ scenario (0.28 µg/m³) in grid cells with non-zero difference from the baseline (Figure S1). This scenario allows us to isolate the effect of regional and race/ethnicity-specific cost data on monetized benefit totals by ensuring there are no differences in concentration changes.

3. Results

3.1. Updated and stratified hospital admission and ED visit costs

3.1.1. Nationwide updated costs and additional costs

For all hospital admission types analyzed, nationwide updated costs differ modestly from default costs in BenMAP-CE (Figure 1a). The greatest difference is for hospital admissions for cardiovascular diseases, which are 24% higher than the default cost. Nationwide updated ED visit costs decreased 35% for cardiovascular diseases and 55% for respiratory diseases compared to default costs. Values in Figure 1a–b are also provided in Table S2 and include disaggregated additional cost types. Details on baseline hospital admission and ED visit counts and rates are provided in Section S3 of the Supplementary Materials.

Additional costs from outpatient surgeries, home health care, and prescribed medicines are substantial for some hospital admission types (Figure 1a; Table S2). With additional costs included, the total cost per hospital admission increases 34% for cardiovascular diseases, 66% for Parkinson's disease, and nearly doubles (95% increase) for respiratory diseases (ages ≤18). The outcomes with higher additional costs are also those with higher numbers of outpatient surgeries per hospital admission; for every 100 hospital admissions, there are an estimated 13.5 outpatient surgeries for cardiovascular diseases, 14.3 for Parkinson's disease, and 113 for respiratory diseases (ages ≤18). Outpatient surgery costs constitute >90% of additional costs for these three hospital admission types. Hospital admission types with lower additional costs, Alzheimer's disease and respiratory diseases (ages ≥65), also have lower outpatient surgery rates (i.e. ≤0.3 per 100 hospital admissions). Home health care costs constitute >80% of additional costs for these two hospital admission types. Prescribed medicines contribute relatively little (0–12%) to additional costs for all hospital admission types.

Additional costs are most substantial for ED visits for cardiovascular diseases (Figure 1b; Table S2). When including all additional costs and wages, the total cost of an ED visit for cardiovascular diseases increases by a factor of 4.6 from \$913 to \$4,230. There are 6.5 outpatient surgery visits per 100 ED visits for cardiovascular diseases, which adds \$2,267 to the total cost (69% of additional costs). Outpatient surgery rates are low for ED visits for respiratory diseases (0.16 per 100 ED visits). Hospital stay costs are substantial for ED visits for cardiovascular diseases (\$990, 30% of additional costs) and respiratory diseases (\$152, 75% of additional costs); 5.3% of such ED visits result in a hospital stay, compared to just 1.4% of ED visits for respiratory diseases.

Figure 1. Comparison of default BenMAP-CE costs to unstratified updated costs and additional costs (a–b) and differences from unstratified updated medical costs by race/ethnicity (c–d), region (e–f), and expected payer type (f–g). Additional costs in (a–b) include outpatient surgery costs, home health care costs, and prescribed medicine costs. Error bars in (c–h) represent 95% confidence intervals. Asterisks in (c–h) denote values that are significantly different (two-sided $p < 0.05$) from the overall updated value; diamonds denote suppressed values. Regional ED visits in (f) are grouped by Census Region, not Census Division as for hospital admissions.

3.1.2. Costs by race/ethnicity

Hospital admission costs vary considerably by racial/ethnic group (Figure 1c). Asian Americans incur the highest costs for four of five hospital admission types and both ED visit types (Figure 1d). Asian Americans pay \$7,620 more (+38%) for hospital admissions for cardiovascular diseases than the overall average of \$20,233, the largest absolute and relative difference of any event type analyzed. The widest cost range between two racial/ethnic groups is also for hospital admissions for cardiovascular diseases, for which Asian Americans pay \$8,408 more per event than Black Americans. White and Black Americans tend to incur below-average hospital admission costs, but the difference from the total population average is typically smaller than the difference for racial/ethnic groups that incur above-average costs.

ED visit costs are higher than average for Asian, Native, and White Americans and lower than average for Black and Hispanic Americans (Figure 1d). ED visit costs for cardiovascular diseases range from -15% from the overall average for Black Americans to +26% for Asian Americans; this range amounts to a difference between the lowest- and highest-cost racial/ethnic groups of \$349 (41% of the overall event cost of \$848). ED visits costs for respiratory diseases are lowest for Hispanic Americans (-15%) and highest for Asian Americans (+24%), a difference of \$171 (39% of the overall event cost of \$443).

3.1.3. Costs by region

Hospital admission costs are highest for all event types in the Pacific region (Figure 1e), which comprises California, Oregon, and Washington. Hospital admission costs for cardiovascular diseases are highest in the Pacific region (\$26,698; +32%) and lowest in the East South Central region (\$17,327; -14%), a difference between the lowest- and highest-cost regions of \$9,371. Regional hospital admission costs for respiratory diseases (ages ≥ 65) differ from the national average by -15% to +43%. Neurological event types have the widest regional hospital admission cost variation; Alzheimer's disease costs differ -34% to +65% and Parkinson's disease costs differ -30% to +46%. Such differences amount to a factor of 2.5 difference in the cost of a hospital admission for Alzheimer's disease between the lowest- and highest-cost regions.

ED visit costs exhibit similar regional patterns as hospital admission costs (Figure 1f), despite their coarser spatial resolution. ED visit costs for cardiovascular and respiratory diseases are highest in the West Census Region (+47% and +24% from the national average, respectively) and lowest in the South Census Region (-22% and -17% from average, respectively). The Pacific region (or encompassing West Census Region) is the only region in which costs differ significantly from national updated costs for all hospital admission and ED visit event types.

Differences in hospital admission and ED visit costs by race/ethnicity (section 3.1.2) partly result from differences in the distribution of racial/ethnic groups by region. In air quality improvement scenarios below (section 3.2), we account for by stratifying costs by race/ethnicity and region simultaneously and reporting benefits per capita. Per-event medical costs are not uniformly highest or lowest for any racial/ethnic groups in all regions when costs are stratified by race/ethnicity and region simultaneously (Figure S2).

3.1.4. Costs by expected payer type

There is modest but significant variation in hospital admission and ED visit costs by expected payer type for some event types (Figure 1g–h). ED visit costs by payer type differ from the all-payer average by –35% to +7.9% for cardiovascular diseases and –28% to +57% for respiratory diseases. Medicaid recipients, patients who self-pay, and patients who are not charged incur modestly but significantly below-average costs for both ED visit types; Medicare patients pay 57% more than the all-payer average for ED visits for respiratory diseases.

3.2. Air quality improvement scenarios

3.2.1. Revised NAAQS scenario

Nationwide benefits from avoided hospital admissions and ED visits and avoided lost wages in the revised PM_{2.5} NAAQS scenario total \$22.9 million when using default cost data (Figure 2b). This total increases by 4.7% to \$24.0 million when using unstratified updated cost data. Stratifying costs by region has a more pronounced effect than stratifying by race/ethnicity; medical benefits total \$25.3 million (+10%) when stratifying by race/ethnicity and \$28.2 million (+23%) when stratifying by region. Stratifying costs by race/ethnicity and region simultaneously produces nearly the same benefit total (\$28.1 million; +23%) as stratifying by region alone.

The inclusion of additional costs further increases the nationwide total benefit to \$37.6 million, a 64% increase from the default benefit total (Figure 2b), when medical costs are stratified by race/ethnicity and region. When including all cost data, total benefits are 43% greater (\$32.7 million) than default when using unstratified medical costs, 49% greater (\$34.3 million) when using medical costs stratified by race, and 65% greater (\$37.8 million) when using medical costs stratified by region. The inclusion of additional benefits substantially increases benefit totals for some hospital admission types: 35% for hospital admissions for cardiovascular diseases, 66% for Parkinson’s disease, and 95% for respiratory diseases (ages ≤18) (Figure 2a). The benefit total from avoided ED visits for cardiovascular diseases, which are –35% from default if only unstratified updated medical costs are included, is a factor of 3.3 higher than default when all additional benefits and wages are included (Figure 2a).

PM_{2.5} reductions occur in 275 counties (8.5% of contiguous U.S. counties) in the revised NAAQS scenario (Figure S3); air quality improvements are unequal and highly concentrated. The influence of regional cost differences on nationwide benefit totals is also evident in county-level results (Figure 2c–f). County-level medical benefits differ from the default by an average of 5.5% (range: –49% to 11%) when using unstratified updated costs, 5.5% (–44% to 25%) when stratifying costs by race/ethnicity, 10% (–32% to 68%) when stratifying costs by region, and 9.5% (–29% to 68%) when stratifying costs by race/ethnicity and region. Although medical benefits decrease in some counties when using updated cost data, total benefits are higher than default in essentially all counties; the average county-level benefit is 48% (range: –1% to 187%) higher when medical costs are stratified by race/ethnicity and region and all additional benefits and wages are included.

Figure 2. Total benefits in the 9/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenario by event type (a) and the sum of all event types (b) using default BenMAP-CE cost data (gray bars) and updated cost data (colored bars) and county-level differences from default medical benefits using updated cost data (c-f), summed across all hospital admission and ED visit event types. Vertical dashed lines in (c-f) show average differences.

Non-White racial/ethnic groups receive a combined 52% of medical benefits from $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ reductions in the revised NAAQS scenario when stratifying medical costs by race/ethnicity and region (Table S3) despite constituting 44% of the population in counties with air quality improvements. White Americans receive 48% (\$12.8 million) of all medical benefits, Hispanic Americans receive 22% (\$5.8 million), Asian Americans receive 17% (\$4.6 million), Black Americans receive 12% (\$3.2 million), and Native Americans receive 0.8% (\$201,000). The distribution of benefits is roughly the same for all event types expect for hospital admissions for respiratory diseases (ages ≤ 18), for which 47% of benefits are experienced by Hispanic Americans.

Figure 3. Per-capita benefit totals and per-capita annual median income in the 9/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scenario by racial/ethnic group and region. Benefit totals use costs stratified by race/ethnicity and region. Horizontal dotted lines show the median per-capita annual income for the total population in each region; vertical dotted lines show the per-capita medical benefits for the total population in each region. Values at the bottom left of panels show differences in population-weighted concentrations (ΔPWC) from the baseline scenario.

On a per-capita basis, Asian Americans (\$173) and Hispanic Americans (\$151) receive higher total benefits nationally than the total population (\$142) in the revised NAAQS scenario (Figure 3). White Americans (\$142) receive the same per-capita benefit as the total population; Black Americans (\$126) and Native Americans (\$133) receive slightly lower per-capita benefits. All racial/ethnic groups receive above-average per-capita benefits in at least one region. Per-capita benefits are largest in the Middle Atlantic (\$38), Pacific (\$34), and East North Central (\$31) regions; per-capita income is higher than the national average in the Middle Atlantic and Pacific regions but lower than average in the East North Central region. The largest population-weighted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration decreases occur in the East South Central and West South Central regions, but per-capita benefits are lower in these regions because hospital admission and ED visits are less costly in these regions. In the Middle Atlantic region, Black Americans (\$40) are the only racial/ethnic group to receive above-average per-capita benefits despite their per-capita income being among the lowest in the region (Figure 3), indicating that Black Americans receive outside benefits relative to their income in this region. In the Pacific region, Native Americans (\$37), Asian Americans (\$37), and White Americans (\$34) receive above-average per-capita benefits, but only Asian and White Americans have above-average per-capita median income.

Medicare recipients (80%; \$21.4 million) receive the largest share of medical benefits in the revised NAAQS scenario, followed by privately insured individuals (9.1%; \$2.4 million) and Medicaid recipients (7.7%; \$2.1 million) (Table S4). For hospital admission types restricted to patients aged ≥ 65 , 86–91% of medical benefits accrue to Medicare recipients, whereas the largest shares accrue to Medicaid (61%) and privately insured (32%) patients for hospital admissions for

cardiovascular diseases (ages ≤ 18). Non-trivial shares of avoided medical costs accrue to individuals who self-pay for ED visits for cardiovascular diseases (4.5%) and respiratory diseases (7.7%).

3.2.2. Alternative NAAQS and uniform improvement scenarios

Total benefits are \$76.7 million in the 8/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenario when using medical costs stratified by race/ethnicity and region (Figure S4), slightly more than twice the total benefit in the revised NAAQS scenario. Total benefits are lower in the more constrained 10/30 and 10/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenarios: \$20.4 million and \$18.6 million (46% and 51% lower than the revised scenario), respectively, when using medical costs stratified by race/ethnicity and region (Figure S5–S6).

Total benefits under all three alternative NAAQS scenarios differ from default totals by the same amount (42–43%) as in the revised NAAQS scenario when using unstratified updated cost data (Figure 4); this finding indicates that the use of unstratified cost data is not strongly influenced by the distribution and magnitude of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration changes. Benefit totals are affected by the nature of air quality changes when stratifying costs by race/ethnicity and region. In both the 10/30 and 10/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenarios, in which $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ reductions are more concentrated than in the revised NAAQS scenario, total benefits are 91% higher than default when medical costs are stratified by race/ethnicity and region (Figure 4); however, in the 8/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenario, in which $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ reductions are more widespread, total benefits are just 51% higher than default.

Figure 4. Difference in total monetized benefits in the revised and alternative NAAQS scenarios and uniform air quality improvement scenario using updated cost data relative to using default BenMAP–CE cost data.

Compared to the revised NAAQS scenario, air quality improvements are more widespread in the more stringent 8/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scenario and more concentrated in the less stringent 10/30 and 10/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scenarios (Figure S3). $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ reductions occur in 857 (27%) counties in the 8/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scenario, 181 (5.6%) in the 10/30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scenario, and 97 (3.0%) in the 10/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scenario. In all the alternative NAAQS scenarios, county-level medical benefits differ from default by nearly the same range as in the revised NAAQS scenario when stratifying costs by race/ethnicity and region, though average changes differ: 8/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scenario, 1.1% (range: -29% to 72%); 10/30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scenario, 24% (range: -29% to 68%); 10/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ scenario, 18% (range: -29% to 68%) (Figure S4–S6).

In the uniform air quality improvement scenario, benefit totals remain largely unchanged (i.e. differ <1%) from the unstratified updated benefit total regardless of whether costs are stratified by race/ethnicity, region, or both (Figure 4). These results indicate that stratified cost inputs have less effect on nationwide benefit totals when air quality changes are more uniformly distributed. In fact, benefit totals under the uniform scenarios differ from the default benefit total only when including avoided costs from outpatient surgeries, home health care, prescribed medicines, and hospital stays originating in the ED (Figure S7).

Despite national benefit totals differing little in the uniform air quality improvement scenario regardless of stratification method, county-level medical benefit totals stratified by race/ethnicity and region differ -1.7% (range: -27% to 76%) from the default benefit totals (Figure S7), a wider range than in any of the NAAQS scenarios. (Noticeable discontinuities in medical benefit differences by Census Divisions in Figure S7 are the result of uniformity in costs within regions and the varying spatial resolution of baseline hospital admission and ED visit rate data; see Figure S8 and Section 4 for details.)

4. Discussion

Our study reveals significant racial/ethnic and regional cost differences for hospital admissions and ED visits associated with ambient $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ exposure in the United States. Asian Americans generally incur the highest medical costs when stratifying costs by race/ethnicity alone, though this is not the case for all event types in all regions when costs are stratified by race/ethnicity and region simultaneously. Costs are highest in the Pacific region, where they can be up to 65% higher than the national average. Our work also introduces a method for incorporating costs of outpatient surgeries, home health care, and prescribed medicines associated with hospital admissions and ED visits, as well as hospital stay costs originating in the ED. These additional costs can add significantly to the costs associated with medical events and are most substantial for hospital admissions for Parkinson's disease and respiratory diseases (ages ≤ 18) and for cardiovascular disease event types.

Applying our cost data to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ reductions that could result from attainment of the revised 9/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS standard, we find that total monetized benefits from avoided hospital admissions and ED visits are 64% higher when stratifying costs by race/ethnicity and region and including additional costs than when using standard BenMAP-CE methods. This finding indicates that current EPA methods underestimate the societal benefits of air quality regulation. We also find that an outside share of benefits would be experienced by non-White Americans in the revised

NAAQS scenario and that a majority of benefits would accrue to Medicare recipients. The effect of cost stratification on monetized totals is more pronounced in scenarios in which PM_{2.5} changes are more concentrated and less pronounced when changes are distributed more widely across the United States. Although nationwide totals are not strongly influenced by cost stratification when air quality improvements are more widespread, county-level medical benefits can differ -27% to $+76\%$ compared to standard BenMAP-CE methods when PM_{2.5} reductions are applied uniformly across the United States. This finding highlights the importance of focusing on more than nationwide totals when assessing the costs and benefits of air quality changes.

Our results are broadly consistent with an analysis using HCUP data that found that individuals in the Pacific region in 2016 had the lowest hospitalization rates but the highest average costs per hospital stay [16]. To our knowledge, only one other study, Birnbaum et al. [26], has estimated additional medical costs for hospital admission types included in BenMAP-CE. Birnbaum et al. calculated costs of cardiovascular and respiratory hospital admissions using a database of privately insured persons, not an all-payer database as in our analysis, and their approach to estimating additional costs differs from our own. The authors identified individuals who were not hospitalized for cardiovascular or respiratory diseases in 2015 but were in 2016; by totaling the costs of ambulatory care (e.g. outpatient visits, home health and other care, and prescribed medicines) and hospital admissions for outcomes other than cardiovascular or respiratory diseases for both years, they estimated the difference in costs between the two years to be the costs associated with hospital admissions for cardiovascular or respiratory diseases. We report that additional costs associated with hospital admissions for cardiovascular and respiratory diseases (ages ≥ 65) add 37% and 17%, respectively, to total per-event costs; Birnbaum et al. report increases of 27% and 24%. (Values from Birnbaum et al. are calculated using data in Exhibit A5; we exclude costs of other hospital admission types, which are not part of our analysis.)

Past research has identified differences in healthcare spending and utilization by race. One study of Medicaid enrollees found that adult Black enrollees sought “primary care and recommended care for acute and chronic conditions” at lower rates than adult White enrollees but had higher rates of ED use in 2016 [14]. After adjusting for demographic characteristics and health status, adult Black enrollees were found to use ED services 16.05 more times per 100 enrollees per year than adult White enrollees. Another study by Dieleman et al. found that American Indian and Alaskan Native (non-Hispanic), multiple-race, and Black (non-Hispanic) individuals used ED care and inpatient care (i.e. hospital admissions) at higher rates than the overall population in 2016 [12]. Asian, Native Hawaiian, and Pacific Islander (non-Hispanic) individuals utilized these types of care at below-average rates, but a higher “price and intensity of services” for this group drove per-person spending back up toward the overall average. Past work has shown that higher ED utilization by race/ethnicity is associated with a lack of access to a primary care doctor or other usual source of care [15]. Our findings show that Black Americans utilize ED care at above-average rates, but this does not hold true for all hospital admission types in our study. Similar to Dieleman et al., we find that Asian Americans utilize inpatient and ED care at below-average rates but pay above-average costs for medical services.

Our analysis is subject to limitations. We use default baseline rates for hospital admissions and ED visits from BenMAP-CE, which are derived from HCUP datasets for 2014 or provided by state health departments and hospital associations for the years between 2011 and 2014 [10]; EPA

assumes that rates are relatively consistent across these years. For states that did not report data, hospital admission and ED visit rates are derived from regional HCUP rates. Baseline rates in BenMAP–CE are provided at the county level; discharge-level data are aggregated to the county level, state-level rates are applied uniformly to all counties in a state, and regional average rates are applied uniformly to counties in a region without discharge- or state-level data. This means that all counties in non-participating states have the same baseline rates. This helps to explain the relatively small county-level, intraregional variation percent differences in monetized benefit in the uniform air quality improvement scenario.

Cost data in this study represent cost-of-illness (COI) estimates, which account for direct costs of medical care and lost wages. COI measures provide a conservative estimate of the benefits of a reduction in risk compared to willingness-to-pay (WTP) estimates that incorporate direct costs as well as other costs such as the value of “reduced pain and suffering” [7]. WTP estimates are not readily available for the health outcomes analyzed in this study [10].

We do not portray the full costs of healthcare utilization related to air pollution exposure since our cost estimates capture ambulatory care and prescribed medicine events that are associated with a hospital admission or ED visit. Past research shows, for example, that pharmaceuticals accounted for nearly half of U.S. asthma spending in 2016, far exceeding the costs of inpatient and emergency care [13]. (BenMAP–CE calculates the economic value of albuterol use associated with asthma symptoms separately from asthma hospital admissions and ED visits.) Other aspects of health equity and health-related economic burdens are also outside the scope of our analysis, including differences in access to health insurance, the prevalence of pre-existing conditions, and healthcare use and cost by income and education level.

There are advantages to the approach we take in this study. Stratified cost data are calculated in a manner consistent with existing BenMAP–CE methodology, which allows for easy comparison of our estimates to those used in BenMAP–CE and for the potential incorporation of our cost data into BenMAP–CE’s modeling framework and future EPA assessments of air pollution–related health costs. The use of datasets with representative coverage across the United States allows for the comparison of costs by race/ethnicity and region; this is an important advantage since national cost data are of limited use in advancing health equity given persistent disparities in PM_{2.5} exposure by region and race/ethnicity [50,51]. Other factors point to the need for more context-specific cost and benefit estimates, including the fact that medical financial hardship in the United States is correlated with educational attainment, health status, and insured status [52]. The methods we describe here are generalizable to other air pollutants, including O₃, NO₂, and sulfur dioxide (SO₂), short-term exposure to which are associated with morbidity outcomes, including respiratory effects [53], as well to other environmental exposures such as extreme heat that are associated with hospital admissions and ED visits [54–57].

Past work has shown the importance of using finely resolved and race/ethnicity–stratified baseline ED visit rate data in air pollution research [23]. One report found that by not stratifying incidence data by race/ethnicity, the number of ED visits for asthma among White people in New Jersey was overestimated by 29% and visits among Black people were underestimated by 91%. Future work should use race/ethnicity–stratified baseline hospital admission and ED visit rates in combination with stratified cost data to further improve monetized cost estimates of medical events. While the

cost data in our study are resolved at the Census Region or Census Division level, state HCUP datasets provide data at the county or zip code level [58]; the use of more finely resolved data was not feasible for this study since datasets must be purchased individually for each participating state. More finely resolved data would be of greater use in studies that resolve exposure estimates and disease incidence at the zip code level [19,21,59]. Past work has identified that health care cost differences can be larger within an area (e.g. hospital referral region, hospital or physician group) than across areas [17], suggesting the importance of using even more fine-scale cost estimates than our regional analysis allows.

Given that mortality effects regularly constitute the vast majority (>90%) of monetized health effects in regulatory impact analyses of PM_{2.5} exposure, our stratified morbidity cost estimates are unlikely to substantially alter total cost or benefit totals. Therefore, unstratified costs may be sufficient for regulatory impact analyses of Clean Air Act regulations since such regulations are primarily concerned with estimating nationwide effects [22,60]. Our stratified estimates are possibly more useful in studies of exposure types, such as acute wildfire smoke, that more often focus on non-fatal health outcomes [61–63] and studies that use BenMAP–CE for health impact analyses at the regional [64,65], state [66], and local scale [25,67,68]. Our cost estimates can be used in combination with recent research defining concentration–response functions for hospital admission and emergency room visits related to PM_{2.5} exposure [69]. The use of our methodology is particularly relevant for analyses with highly concentrated exposure changes, as opposed to scenarios with more uniform and widespread nationwide effects, given the spatially variable nature of cost estimates.

This work provides a starting point for further refinements to cost stratification. Future work could determine cost breakdowns by household income and quarter of the year, both of which are data elements included in HCUP datasets. Costs by quarter of the year are particularly relevant for analyses focused on exposures that are often analyzed in terms of daily (e.g. wildfire smoke) or seasonal (e.g. ground-level ozone) health harms. Studies that use similar methods to stratify costs should use estimates stratified by both race/ethnicity and region to account for the unequal distribution of racial/ethnic groups across the United States.

5. Conclusion

Numerous factors are converging to impose higher air pollution–related health care costs on governments, health care providers, and individuals. Health care spending is much higher in the United States than other high-income countries, yet Americans have lower health care coverage rates and generally suffer worse health outcomes despite this greater expense [70]. Health care premiums continue to rise [71], and health care spending is expected to increase in the near future, reflecting expected higher prices for health care goods and services, a growing population of Americans eligible for Medicare, and generally increased use and intensity of health care services [72]. At the same time, climate change is increasing health-related costs of climate-sensitive extreme events [33], including documented air quality degradations from the growing influence of wildfire smoke PM_{2.5} in parts of the United States [73,74]. It is important that analyses documenting the economic burden of air pollution – and economic benefits of air quality improvements – use health care cost data that are as refined and comprehensive as possible.

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References

1. Hay SI, Ong KL, Santomauro DF, A B, Aalipour MA, Aalruz H, et al. Burden of 375 diseases and injuries, risk-attributable burden of 88 risk factors, and healthy life expectancy in 204 countries and territories, including 660 subnational locations, 1990–2023: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2023. *The Lancet*. 2025 Oct 18;406(10513):1873–922.
2. Lelieveld J, Klingmüller K, Pozzer A, Burnett RT, Haines A, Ramanathan V. Effects of fossil fuel and total anthropogenic emission removal on public health and climate. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 2019 Apr 9;116(15):7192–7.
3. Tessum CW, Apte JS, Goodkind AL, Muller NZ, Mullins KA, Paoletta DA, et al. Inequity in consumption of goods and services adds to racial–ethnic disparities in air pollution exposure. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 2019 Mar 26;116(13):6001–6.
4. Mailloux NA, Abel DW, Holloway T, Patz JA. Nationwide and Regional PM_{2.5}-Related Air Quality Health Benefits from the Removal of Energy-Related Emissions in the United States. *GeoHealth*. 2022 May;6(5). Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2022GH000603>
5. US EPA. Integrated Science Assessment for Particulate Matter (December 2019). US EPA; 2019 Dec p. 1967.
6. US EPA. Supplement to the 2019 Integrated Science Assessment for Particulate Matter. 2022.
7. Sacks JD, Lloyd JM, Zhu Y, Anderton J, Jang CJ, Hubbell B, et al. The Environmental Benefits Mapping and Analysis Program – Community Edition (BenMAP–CE): A tool to estimate the health and economic benefits of reducing air pollution. *Environmental Modelling & Software*. 2018 June;104:118–29.
8. US EPA. Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}) Trends. 2024. Available from: <https://www.epa.gov/air-trends/particulate-matter-pm25-trends>
9. US EPA. The Benefits and Costs of the Clean Air Act from 1990 to 2020. 2011 Apr.
10. US EPA. Environmental Benefits Mapping and Analysis Program Community Edition (BenMAP-CE): User’s Manual. 2022 Jan.
11. US EPA. Regulatory Impact Analysis for the Proposed Reconsideration of the National Ambient Air Quality Standards for Particulate Matter. 2022 Dec;
12. Dieleman JL, Chen C, Crosby SW, Liu A, McCracken D, Pollock IA, et al. US Health Care Spending by Race and Ethnicity, 2002–2016. *JAMA*. 2021 Aug 17;326(7):649.
13. Duan KI, Birger M, Au DH, Spece LJ, Feemster LC, Dieleman JL. Health Care Spending on Respiratory Diseases in the United States, 1996–2016. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2023;207(2):183–92.
14. Wallace J, Lollo A, Duchowny KA, Lavalley M, Ndumele CD. Disparities in Health Care Spending and Utilization Among Black and White Medicaid Enrollees. *JAMA Health Forum*. 2022 June 10;3(6):e221398.
15. Parast L, Mathews M, Martino S, Lehrman WG, Stark D, Elliott MN. Racial/Ethnic Differences in Emergency Department Utilization and Experience. *J GEN INTERN MED*. 2022 Jan 1;37(1):49–56.
16. Freeman WJ, Weiss AJ, Heslin KC. Overview of U.S. Hospital Stays in 2016: Variation by Geographic Region. Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality; 2018 Dec. (HCUP Statistical Brief). Report No.: #246. Available from: <https://hcup-us.ahrq.gov/reports/statbriefs/sb246-Geographic-Variation-Hospital-Stays.jsp>
17. Institute of Medicine. Variation in health care spending: target decision making, not geography. Washington, DC: National Academy of Sciences; 2013 p. 51–4556–51–4556. Available from: <http://choicereviews.org/review/10.5860/CHOICE.51-4556>
18. Carter TS, Kerr GH, Amini H, Martin RV, Oviennhada U, Schwartz J, et al. PM_{2.5} data inputs alter identification of disadvantaged communities. *Environ Res Lett*. 2023 Oct;18(11):114008.

19. Castillo MD, Kinney PL, Southerland V, Arno CA, Crawford K, van Donkelaar A, et al. Estimating Intra-Urban Inequities in PM2.5-Attributable Health Impacts: A Case Study for Washington, DC. *Geohealth*. 2021 Nov;5(11). Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2021GH000431>
20. Fann N, Roman HA, Fulcher CM, Gentile MA, Hubbell BJ, Wesson K, et al. Maximizing Health Benefits and Minimizing Inequality: Incorporating Local-Scale Data in the Design and Evaluation of Air Quality Policies. *Risk Analysis*. 2011;31(6):908–22.
21. Southerland VA, Anenberg SC, Harris M, Apte J, Hystad P, van Donkelaar A, et al. Assessing the Distribution of Air Pollution Health Risks within Cities: A Neighborhood-Scale Analysis Leveraging High-Resolution Data Sets in the Bay Area, California. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2021 Mar;129(3):EHP7679, 037006.
22. Hubbell B, Fann N, Levy JI. Methodological considerations in developing local-scale health impact assessments: balancing national, regional, and local data. *Air Qual Atmos Health*. 2009 June;2(2):99–110.
23. Industrial Economics, Inc. Analysis of PM2.5-Related Health Burdens Under Current and Alternative NAAQS. 2022.
24. Spiller E, Proville J, Roy A, Muller NZ. Mortality Risk from PM2.5: A Comparison of Modeling Approaches to Identify Disparities across Racial/Ethnic Groups in Policy Outcomes. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2021 Dec;129(12):127004.
25. Kheirbek I, Wheeler K, Walters S, Kass D, Matte T. PM2.5 and ozone health impacts and disparities in New York City: sensitivity to spatial and temporal resolution. *Air Qual Atmos Health*. 2013 June 1;6(2):473–86.
26. Birnbaum HG, Carley CD, Desai U, Ou S, Zuckerman PR. Measuring The Impact Of Air Pollution On Health Care Costs. *Health Affairs*. 2020 Dec 1;39(12):2113–9.
27. Federal Register. Reconsideration of the National Ambient Air Quality Standards for Particulate Matter. 2024. Report No.: RIN 2060–AV52.
28. AHRQ. HCUP National Inpatient Sample (NIS). 2019. Available from: <https://hcup-us.ahrq.gov/nisoverview.jsp>
29. AHRQ. HCUP National Emergency Department Sample (NEDS). 2019. Available from: <https://hcup-us.ahrq.gov/nedsoverview.jsp>
30. Cassell K, Zipfel CM, Bansal S, Weinberger DM. Trends in non-COVID-19 hospitalizations prior to and during the COVID-19 pandemic period, United States, 2017–2021. *Nat Commun*. 2022 Oct 8;13(1):5930.
31. AHRQ. HCUP National Ambulatory Surgery Sample. 2019. Available from: <https://hcup-us.ahrq.gov/nassoverview.jsp>
32. AHRQ. Medical Expenditure Panel Survey. 2019. Available from: <https://meps.ahrq.gov/mepsweb/index.jsp>
33. Limaye VS, Max W, Constible J, Knowlton K. Estimating the Health-Related Costs of 10 Climate-Sensitive U.S. Events During 2012. *GeoHealth*. 2019 Sept 17;2019GH000202.
34. AHRQ. HCUP Online Tutorial Series. 2023. Available from: https://hcup-us.ahrq.gov/tech_assist/tutorials.jsp
35. US Census Bureau. 2019 Population Estimates by Age, Sex, Race and Hispanic Origin. 2020. Available from: <https://www.census.gov/newsroom/press-kits/2020/population-estimates-detailed.html>
36. US Census Bureau. 2019 Data Release Schedule. 2020. Available from: <https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/acs/news/data-releases/2019/release-schedule.html>
37. US EPA. Estimating PM2.5- and Ozone-Attributable Health Benefits: 2024 Update. 2024 June.
38. AHRQ. Cost-to-Charge Ratio. 2021. Available from: <https://hcup-us.ahrq.gov/db/ccr/costtocharge.jsp>
39. Arora V, Moriates C, Shah N. The Challenge of Understanding Health Care Costs and Charges. *AMA Journal of Ethics*. 2015 Nov 1;17(11):1046–52.
40. Pickens G, Liang L, Roemer M. HCUP Cost-to-Charge Ratio Methodologies. US Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality; 2021 Dec. (HCUP Method Series). Report No.: 2021–05.
41. NBER. ICD-9-CM to and from ICD-10-CM and ICD-10-PCS Crosswalk or General Equivalence Mappings. NBER. 2024. Available from: <https://www.nber.org/research/data/icd-9-cm-and-icd-10-cm-and-icd-10-pcs-crosswalk-or-general-equivalence-mappings>
42. AHRQ. HCUP Nationwide Data Use Agreement. 2024. Available from: <https://hcup-us.ahrq.gov/team/NationwideDUA.jsp>
43. US BLS. BLS Data Viewer: Medical care. 2024. Available from: <https://data.bls.gov/dataViewer/view/timeseries/CUUR0000SAM>
44. Karaca Z, Wong HS, Mutter RL. Duration of patients' visits to the hospital emergency department. *BMC Emerg Med*. 2012 Nov 6;12(1):15.
45. Russell LB, Ibuka Y, Carr D. How Much Time Do Patients Spend on Outpatient Visits?: The American Time Use Survey. *The Patient: Patient-Centered Outcomes Research*. 2008 July;1(3):211–22.

46. Sanders GD, Neumann PJ, Basu A, Brock DW, Feeny D, Krahn M, et al. Recommendations for Conduct, Methodological Practices, and Reporting of Cost-effectiveness Analyses: Second Panel on Cost-Effectiveness in Health and Medicine. *JAMA*. 2016 Sept 13;316(10):1093.
47. US EPA. Revised Cross-State Air Pollution Rule Update. 2021. Available from: <https://www.epa.gov/Cross-State-Air-Pollution/revised-cross-state-air-pollution-rule-update>
48. US EPA. The Safer Affordable Fuel Efficient (SAFE) Vehicles Final Rule for Model Years 2021-2026. 2020. Available from: <https://www.epa.gov/regulations-emissions-vehicles-and-engines/safer-affordable-fuel-efficient-safe-vehicles-final-rule>
49. US EPA. NSPS for GHG Emissions from New, Modified, and Reconstructed Electric Utility Generating Units. 2015. Available from: <https://www.epa.gov/stationary-sources-air-pollution/nsps-ghg-emissions-new-modified-and-reconstructed-electric-utility>
50. Jbaily A, Zhou X, Liu J, Lee TH, Kamareddine L, Verguet S, et al. Air pollution exposure disparities across US population and income groups. *Nature*. 2022 Jan 13;601(7892):228–33.
51. Colmer J, Hardman I, Shimshack J, Voorheis J. Disparities in PM_{2.5} air pollution in the United States. *Science*. 2020 July 31;369(6503):575–8.
52. Yabroff KR, Zhao J, Han X, Zheng Z. Prevalence and Correlates of Medical Financial Hardship in the USA. *J GEN INTERN MED*. 2019 Aug;34(8):1494–502.
53. Coffman E, Rappold AG, Nethery RC, Anderton J, Amend M, Jackson MA, et al. Quantifying Multipollutant Health Impacts Using the Environmental Benefits Mapping and Analysis Program—Community Edition (BenMAP-CE): A Case Study in Atlanta, Georgia. *Environmental Health Perspectives*. 2024 Mar;132(3):037003.
54. Bernstein AS, Sun S, Weinberger KR, Spangler KR, Sheffield PE, Wellenius GA. Warm Season and Emergency Department Visits to U.S. Children’s Hospitals. *Environmental Health Perspectives*. 2022 Jan;130(1):017001.
55. Guirguis K, Gershunov A, Tardy A, Basu R. The Impact of Recent Heat Waves on Human Health in California. 2014 Jan; Available from: <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/apme/53/1/jamc-d-13-0130.1.xml>
56. Hess JJ, Saha S, Lubber G. Summertime Acute Heat Illness in U.S. Emergency Departments from 2006 through 2010: Analysis of a Nationally Representative Sample. *Environmental Health Perspectives*. 2014 Nov;122(11):1209–15.
57. Limaye VS, Vargo J, Harkey M, Holloway T, Patz JA. Climate Change and Heat-Related Excess Mortality in the Eastern USA. *EcoHealth*. 2018 Sept;15(3):485–96.
58. US AHRQ. HCUP-US Databases. 2022. Available from: <https://hcup-us.ahrq.gov/databases.jsp>
59. Darling R, Hansen K, Aguilera R, Basu R, Benmarhnia T, Letellier N. The Burden of Wildfire Smoke on Respiratory Health in California at the Zip Code Level: Uncovering the Disproportionate Impacts of Differential Fine Particle Composition. *GeoHealth*. 2023;7(10):e2023GH000884.
60. OMB. Circular A-4. The White House. 2003. Available from: <https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/node/15644>
61. Reid CE, Considine EM, Watson GL, Telesca D, Pfister GG, Jerrett M. Effect modification of the association between fine particulate air pollution during a wildfire event and respiratory health by area-level measures of socio-economic status, race/ethnicity, and smoking prevalence. *Environ Res: Health*. 2023 Apr;1(2):025005.
62. Aguilera R, Corringham T, Gershunov A, Benmarhnia T. Wildfire smoke impacts respiratory health more than fine particles from other sources: observational evidence from Southern California. *Nat Commun*. 2021 Dec;12(1):1493.
63. Cleland SE, Serre ML, Rappold AG, West JJ. Estimating the Acute Health Impacts of Fire-Originated PM_{2.5} Exposure During the 2017 California Wildfires: Sensitivity to Choices of Inputs. *GeoHealth*. 2021 July;5(7). Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2021GH000414>
64. Grabow ML, Spak SN, Holloway T, Stone B, Mednick AC, Patz JA. Air Quality and Exercise-Related Health Benefits from Reduced Car Travel in the Midwestern United States. *Environmental Health Perspectives*. 2012 Jan;120(1):68–76.
65. Thompson TM, Saari RK, Selin NE. Air quality resolution for health impact assessment: influence of regional characteristics. *Atmos Chem Phys*. 2014 Jan 28;14(2):969–78.
66. Zhu S, Kinnon MM, Paradise A, Dabdub D, Samuelsen GS. Health Benefits in California of Strengthening the Fine Particulate Matter Standards. *Environ Sci Technol*. 2021 Sept 21;55(18):12223–32.
67. Stewart DR, Saunders E, Perea RA, Fitzgerald R, Campbell DE, Stockwell WR. Linking Air Quality and Human Health Effects Models: An Application to the Los Angeles Air Basin. *Environ Health Insights*. 2017 Nov 13;11:1178630217737551.

68. Wesson K, Fann N, Morris M, Fox T, Hubbell B. A multi-pollutant, risk-based approach to air quality management: Case study for Detroit. *Atmospheric Pollution Research*. 2010 Oct 1;1(4):296–304.
69. Ru M, Shindell D, Spadaro JV, Lamarque JF, Challapalli A, Wagner F, et al. New concentration-response functions for seven morbidity endpoints associated with short-term PM_{2.5} exposure and their implications for health impact assessment. *Environment International*. 2023 Sept;179:108122.
70. Papanicolas I, Woskie LR, Jha AK. Health Care Spending in the United States and Other High-Income Countries. *JAMA*. 2018 Mar 13;319(10):1024.
71. Claxton G, Rae M, Damico A, Winger A, Wager E. Health Benefits In 2025: Family Premiums Rise 6 Percent, Large Employers Increase Coverage Of GLP-1s For Weight Loss: Article reports the results of the annual KFF Employer Health Benefits Survey. *Health Affairs*. 2025 Nov 1;44(11):1359–68.
72. Keehan SP, Madison AJ, Poisal JA, Cuckler GA, Smith SD, Sisko AM, et al. National Health Expenditure Projections, 2024–33: Despite Insurance Coverage Declines, Health To Grow As Share Of GDP.
73. Burke M, Childs ML, de la Cuesta B, Qiu M, Li J, Gould CF, et al. The contribution of wildfire to PM_{2.5} trends in the USA. *Nature*. 2023 Sept 20;1–6.
74. Fann N, Alman B, Broome RA, Morgan GG, Johnston FH, Pouliot G, et al. The health impacts and economic value of wildland fire episodes in the U.S.: 2008–2012. *Science of The Total Environment*. 2018 Jan 1;610–611:802–9.

Supplementary Materials for

Improved accounting of the health costs of air pollution in the United States

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S1. HCUP dataset weighting procedure

HCUP provides an Online Training Tutorial Series that provides data users with methods for conducting research with HCUP data (https://hcup-us.ahrq.gov/tech_assist/tutorials.jsp). The tutorial on “Producing National HCUP Estimates,” which provides methods for producing national and regional weighted estimates, uses the 2019 National Inpatient Sample (NIS), the same inpatient dataset used in our analysis. Example SAS code is provided that calculates national weighted estimates for hospital admissions with a primary diagnosis of asthma, based on the Clinical Classification Software Refined (CCSR) diagnosis code for asthma (RSP009). We replicate these methods using an analogous function in R. In the case of NIS data, NIS hospital identifiers are used as the cluster ID (ids) variable, NIS stratum identifiers as the strata variable, and NIS discharge weights as the weights variable. Results from both methods are listed below (SAS code output are taken from the data summary on the HCUP website):

SAS code:

Number of strata: 201
Number of clusters: 4,568
Number of observations: 7,083,805
Sum of weights: 35,419,023
Sum: 169,330

R code:

Number of strata: 201
Number of clusters: 4,568
Number of observations: 7,083,805
Sum of weights: 35,419,023
Sum: 169,330

S2. HCUP data partners

HCUP data partners include: Alaska Department of Health; Alaska Hospital and Healthcare Association; Arizona Department of Health Services; Arkansas Department of Health; California Department of Health Care Access and Information; Colorado Hospital Association; Connecticut Hospital Association; Delaware Division of Public Health; District of Columbia Hospital Association; Florida Agency for Health Care Administration; Georgia Hospital Association; University of Hawaii, Hilo Center for Rural Health Science; Hawaii Lauilima Data Alliance; Illinois Department of Public Health; Indiana Hospital Association; Iowa Hospital Association;

Kansas Hospital Association; Kentucky Cabinet for Health and Family Services; Louisiana Department of Health; Maine Health Data Organization; Maryland Health Services Cost Review Commission; Massachusetts Center for Health Information and Analysis; Michigan Health & Hospital Association; Minnesota Hospital Association (provides data for Minnesota and North Dakota hospitals); Mississippi State Department of Health; Missouri Hospital Industry Data Institute; Montana Hospital Association; Nebraska Hospital Association; Nevada Department of Health and Human Services; New Hampshire Department of Health & Human Services; New Jersey Department of Health; New Mexico Department of Health; New York State Department of Health; North Carolina Department of Health and Human Services; North Dakota (data provided by the Minnesota Hospital Association); Ohio Hospital Association; Oklahoma State Department of Health; Oregon Health Authority; Oregon Association of Hospitals and Health Systems; Pennsylvania Health Care Cost Containment Council; Rhode Island Department of Health; South Carolina Revenue and Fiscal Affairs Office; South Dakota Association of Healthcare Organizations; Tennessee Hospital Association; Texas Department of State Health Services; Utah Department of Health; Vermont Association of Hospitals and Health Systems; Virginia Health Information; Washington State Department of Health; West Virginia Department of Health and Human Resources; Wisconsin Department of Health Services; Wyoming Hospital Association

S3. Baseline hospital admission and ED visit counts and rates

The weighted HCUP datasets used in this study contain records of 35.4 million hospital discharges, 143.4 million ED visits, and 11.9 million elective outpatient surgeries in 2019. This includes 3.47 million hospital admissions for cardiovascular diseases, 2.01 million for respiratory diseases, 42,200 for Alzheimer's disease, and 18,400 for Parkinson's disease as well as 5.89 million ED visits for cardiovascular diseases and 10.9 million for respiratory diseases.

National hospital discharge rates per 10,000 persons for each modeled event type are as follows: Alzheimer's disease (3.93), cardiovascular (95.8), respiratory for patients aged ≤ 18 (16.1), respiratory for patients aged ≥ 65 (76.4), and Parkinson's disease (1.71). ED visit rates are 90.2 per 10,000 persons for cardiovascular diseases and 167 for respiratory diseases. Figure S9 shows differences from overall rates by race/ethnicity and region. Rates are lower than average for Asian and Hispanic Americans for all hospital admission and ED visit types. Black Americans consistently have the highest ED visit rates. Hospital admission rates are lower than average in the Pacific region for all outcomes.

Figure S1. Differences in grid cell-level PM_{2.5} concentrations in the 9/35 µg/m³ NAAQS scenario relative to the baseline.

Figure S2. Difference in per-event medical costs from overall regional costs by race/ethnicity.

Figure S3. Decreases in PM_{2.5} concentrations under NAAQS scenarios. County borders are shown if they overlap grid cells in which PM_{2.5} concentration decreases occur.

Figure S4. Total benefits in the 8/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenario by event type (a) and the sum of all event types (b) using default BenMAP-CE cost data (gray bars) and updated cost data (colored bars) and county-level differences from default medical benefits using updated cost data (c-f), summed across all hospital admission and ED visit event types. Vertical dashed lines in (c-f) show average differences.

Figure S5. Total benefits in the 10/30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenario by event type (a) and the sum of all event types (b) using default BenMAP-CE cost data (gray bars) and updated cost data (colored bars) and county-level differences from default medical benefits using updated cost data (c-f), summed across all hospital admission and ED visit event types. Vertical dashed lines in (c-f) show average differences.

Figure S6. Total benefits in the 10/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenario by event type (a) and the sum of all event types (b) using default BenMAP-CE cost data (gray bars) and updated cost data (colored bars) and county-level differences from default medical benefits using updated cost data (c-f), summed across all hospital admission and ED visit event types. Vertical dashed lines in (c-f) show average differences.

Figure S7. Total benefits in the uniform air quality improvement scenario by event type (a) and the sum of all event types (b) using default BenMAP-CE cost data (gray bars) and updated cost data (colored bars) and county-level differences from default medical benefits using updated cost data (c-f), summed across all hospital admission and ED visit event types. Vertical dashed lines in (c-f) show average differences.

Figure S8. Resolution of HCUP data used to derive baseline hospital admission rates in BenMAP-CE.

Figure S9. Differences from overall updated baseline hospital admission and ED visit rates.

Table S1. Race/ethnicity classifications by data source

HCUP	U.S. Census Bureau		BenMAP-CE	
	Race	Ethnicity	Race	Ethnicity
White	White	Not Hispanic	White	Non-Hispanic
Black	Black or African American	Not Hispanic	African American	Non-Hispanic
Hispanic	All races	Hispanic	All races	Hispanic
Asian or Pacific Islander	Asian; Native Hawaiian and Other Pacific Islander	Not Hispanic	Asian	Non-Hispanic
Native American	American Indian or Alaska Native	Not Hispanic	American Indian	Non-Hispanic
Other	Two or more races	Not Hispanic	–	–

Table S2. Per-event medical event (2019 U.S. dollars)

	Hospital admissions				ED visits		
	Alzheimer's disease (ages ≥65)	Cardiovascular (ages ≥65)	Parkinson's disease (ages ≥65)	Respiratory (ages ≤18)	Respiratory (ages ≥65)	Cardiovascular (all ages)	Respiratory (all ages)
<i>Default costs</i>							
Medical event	11,933	16,361	13,600	10,125	10,045	1,295	976
Wages	1,531	928	737	673	896	–	–
Total	13,464	17,289	14,337	10,797	10,941	1,295	976
<i>Updated costs, unstratified</i>							
Medical event	13,280	20,233	13,163	9,512	10,161	848	443
Wages	1,252	577	864	436	592	66	66
Outpatient surgeries	37	5,918	7,594	9,183	34	2,267	13
Wages	0	4	5	37	0	2	0
Home health care	249	257	402	1	402	9	3
Wages	1,260	943	1,198	183	1,284	37	12
Hospital stay originating in the ED	–	–	–	–	–	990	152
Prescribed medicines	0	35	83	24	57	12	35
Total	16,078	27,967	23,308	19,377	12,530	4,230	723

Table S3. Monetized benefits from avoided medical events by race/ethnicity in the 9/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenario (2019 U.S. dollars)

Racial/ethnic group	Hospital admissions				ED visits		Total	
	Alzheimer's disease (ages ≥ 65)	Cardiovascular (ages ≥ 65)	Parkinson's disease (ages ≥ 65)	Respiratory (ages ≤ 18)	Respiratory (ages ≥ 65)	Cardiovascular (all ages)		Respiratory (all ages)
<i>Default costs</i>								
White	5,650,982	2,675,003	891,883	472,022	249,379	377,543	427,196	10,744,008
Black	1,339,155	669,851	225,629	252,919	63,745	112,898	185,723	2,849,920
Hispanic	1,697,081	1,020,131	318,839	747,351	96,516	201,439	439,980	4,521,337
Asian	1,413,414	717,662	211,013	179,997	66,960	111,686	144,459	2,845,191
Native	49,046	28,191	9,014	18,361	2,630	5,401	11,111	123,754
Total	10,149,679	5,110,838	1,656,378	1,670,649	479,229	808,968	1,208,469	21,084,210
<i>Updated costs, stratified by race/ethnicity and region</i>								
White	7,094,168	3,490,717	934,641	449,323	280,801	295,727	238,672	12,784,050
Black	1,537,352	879,963	254,198	252,404	76,348	72,987	78,415	3,151,668
Hispanic	2,636,571	1,452,841	401,946	837,534	116,266	150,033	168,140	5,763,331
Asian	2,517,013	1,309,022	277,638	226,548	98,637	102,596	85,013	4,616,466
Native	106,808	49,953	9,913	20,535	3,983	4,548	5,756	201,495
Total	13,891,912	7,182,497	1,878,337	1,786,344	576,035	625,890	575,996	26,517,011

Note: Values include costs from avoided medical events but do not include associated wages or additional costs.

Table S4. Monetized benefits from avoided medical events by expected payer in the 9/35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NAAQS scenario (2019 U.S. dollars)

Expected payer	Hospital admissions				ED visits			Total
	Alzheimer's disease (ages ≥ 65)	Cardiovascular (ages ≥ 65)	Parkinson's disease (ages ≥ 65)	Respiratory (ages ≤ 18)	Respiratory (ages ≥ 65)	Cardiovascular (all ages)	Respiratory (all ages)	
<i>Default costs</i>								
Medicare	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Medicaid	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Private	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Self-pay	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
No charge	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Other	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Total	10,149,679	5,110,838	1,656,378	1,670,649	479,229	808,968	1,208,469	21,084,210
<i>Updated costs, stratified by expected payer and region</i>								
Medicare	12,537,026	6,070,368	1,687,714	1,797	509,617	362,310	198,243	21,367,075
Medicaid	499,121	172,793	22,550	1,081,830	16,403	77,495	190,649	2,060,841
Private	766,456	648,470	124,437	564,817	34,785	144,270	142,018	2,425,252
Self-pay	86,561	51,073	4,058	35,254	2,693	28,192	46,132	253,964
No charge	1,871	2,198	146	246	188	1,092	1,549	7,290
Other	166,319	144,536	25,146	102,992	8,252	16,157	17,310	480,712
Total	14,057,355	7,089,438	1,864,051	1,786,935	571,937	629,516	595,902	26,595,134

Note: Values include costs from avoided medical events but do not include associated wages or additional costs.